

AI-DRIVEN PHYSICAL AND MONETARY VALUATION OF PROVISIONING AND REGULATORY ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN SRI LANKA

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Abstract

Monetary value of ecosystem Service of Sri Lanka are not available due to data and computational limitations. This paper investigated the application of AI-driven modeling platform “SEEA EA”. The physical and monetary values of provisioning and regulatory ecosystem services of Sri Lanka are generated and discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Physical and monetary values of ecosystem services in Sri Lanka is scarce mainly due to non-availability of data and computational complexity. The AI-driven modeling platform SEEA EA use remote sensing and GIS data and it is freely available for valuation of ecosystem services. However, SEEA EA (2021) reported that awareness on this tool and its application is poor in Sri Lanka (Figure 1) as no research paper published using this tool by early July, 2025. Chandrasiri (2025) estimated changes in ecosystems extent in Sri Lanka using SEEA EA. The changes in ecosystem condition variable, condition indicator and condition index that are estimated using SEEA EA are reported by Chandrasiri (2025). The objective of this study is to assess the monetary value of ecosystem services.

Valuation of ecosystem services is needed and important as quantification of ecosystem services help value diverse benefits humans derive from nature including tangible resources like food and timber, as well as intangible benefits such as climate regulation and cultural value. Therefore, a study has been carried out to value physical and monetary ecosystem services in Sri Lanka and to create awareness on potential and limitation of SEEA EA tool.

The measurement of ecosystem services is required to explain the variety of contributions that ecosystems make to people and the economy. More often, the attention is on marketable goods such as crops, timber and fish. But true ecosystem services extend well beyond normal such as air filtration, water purification, global climate regulation and recreation-related services. The focus of accounting for ecosystem services is to provide a clear description of the range of these services, the spatial heterogeneity of their delivery, and the local to global beneficiaries of these services, in order that this information can be readily compared between and connected to the different ecosystems that supply the services.

Figure 1. Global SEEA EA implementation

METHODOLOGY

The SEEA EA AI modeling platform (SEEA EA, 2021) was used to assess the physical and monetary value of ecosystems in Sri Lanka. Presumably, SEEA EA has data gaps before 2005 period for Sri Lanka. Moreover, it is reported that SEEA EA use 2005 as a base year. As a result, machine learning computations jammed at the year 2005. Therefore, the ecosystem services data were generated for years 2005 and 2018.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ecosystem Services (physical) of Sri Lanka (2005-2018)

SEEA EA (2021) defined ecosystem services as “the measurable contributions of ecosystems to benefits used by people.” This definition emphasizes that ecosystem services represent the flows of benefits that ecosystems provide to human society, which can be measured and accounted for in both physical and monetary terms. The ecosystem services are classified into four groups, namely, **supporting** (nutrient cycling, soil formation, primary production etc.), **provisioning** (biomass, food, fresh water, wood and fiber and fuel etc.), **regulating** (climate regulation, flood regulation, disease regulation, pollination and water purification etc.) and **cultural** (aesthetic, spiritual, educational and recreational etc.) services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The generic set of variables generated by SEEA for each service are shown in Table 1. Data for some of these variables are generated by SEEA and they are discussed in this section.

Table 1. The generic set of ecosystem services variables generated by SEEA

Ecosystem service	Variable	Units of measure
Provisioning services		
Biomass provisioning	Crop provisioning	tonnes
	Wood(Timber) provisioning	m ³
	Wild fish and other natural aquatic biomass provisioning	tonnes
Regulating and maintenance services		
Global climate regulation services	Carbon storage	tonnes CO ₂
Water purification services	N removed	tonnes N removed
Crop Pollination	crop production	tonnes
Cultural services		
Recreation-related services	site visits	# visits

Crop Provisioning Ecosystem Service in Physical Terms (Tonnes):2005-2018 Crop provisioning services are defined as the ecosystem contributions to the growth of cultivated plants harvested for food, fiber, fodder, and energy. The crop provisioning service physical supply (2005-2018) is shown in Tables 2.

Table 2. Crop provisioning service physical supply (tonnes): 2005-2018

Crop provisioning	Soy Bean	Wheat	Rice	SugarCane	Potato	Maize	Sunflower
Production 2005 (tons)	980	3	2,101,394	4,976,022	18,162	155,757	11,830
Production 2018 (tons)	649	4	2,609,900	7,659,569	24,024	322,073	1,644
Net change	-331	1	508,506	2,683,547	5,862	166,316	-10185

source: generated by SEEA EA

SEEA EA AI platform generates national crop production data of seven crops as indicators of crop provisioning service of ecosystems in Sri Lanka (Table 2). The production values indicate the crop provisioning service of the ecosystems in physical terms (Tonnes). Examination of data revealed that except in soybean and sunflower, production has increased in rice (24%), sugarcane (53%), potato (32%), and maize (106%).

The question arises naturally is how the crop production data of few crops indicate the crop provisioning service of the forest ecosystems of the country. The most significant issue is that the forest ecosystems are situated far away from croplands, perhaps, in a totally different agro-climatic zone of Sri Lanka. Furthermore, more than one forest ecosystem is contributing to crop provisioning services.

It is reported that forest ecosystems contribute to crop production via regulation of climate, water supply, pollination, genetics and soil fertility, especially, chemical state (e.g., soil organic carbon, nutrients). These ecosystem services may occur in locations far away from croplands, yet contributes to production. Moreover, the crop provisioning services could be separated into two parts, i.e. ecosystem contribution (natural inputs like sunlight, rain, soil fertility) and human contribution (planting, chemicals, machinery). The ecosystem share of crop production could be minimum and difficult to estimate with high intensity agriculture using chemical fertilizer, high quality seeds and other production technology. Thus, total crop production data are used as a proxy of biomass production. Therefore, the national crop production cannot be attributed solely to crop provisioning service of a given ecosystem. According to statistics of the Department of Agriculture, Sri Lanka, rice production in 2017 and 2018 are 2,383,153 and 3,929,831 tonnes respectively (Agstat, 2019). The reported numbers by ARIES SEEA EA are more or less similar to actual yields reported, suggesting, healthy functioning of ecosystems.

“Cropland” is an ecosystem according to SEEA EA classification system. The other considerations related to crop provisioning service is that yields are not harvested “in-situ”. In situ means, ecosystem services are supplied in a location, and it is used and benefits are received in the same location. For example, timber is a provisioning ecosystem service that is directly harvested from forest ecosystems. Thus, timber is an in-situ benefit. However, rice crop is not typically "harvested from ecosystems" in the same way as timber from forests. Rice is cultivated through intensive agricultural practices involving significant human management inputs such as planting, irrigation, fertilization, and pest control. The ecosystem's role for rice is modeled as providing the natural conditions that support crop growth, but the actual rice yield is largely a product of managed agroecosystems rather than a natural ecosystem service harvested in situ. Therefore, crop yields cannot be interpreted as a results of ecosystem services of an “cropland” ecosystem in a given location. Regulating and maintenance services are commonly supplied by ecosystems, or combinations of ecosystems, in one location and used by economic units in other. Thus, it can be concluded that national crop yields are due to collective supporting and regulating services of ecosystems of Sri Lanka.

The most important issue of concern is that crop production data of seven crops (Soybean, wheat, rice, sunflower, sugarcane, potato and maize) generated by ARIES SEEA EA is not sufficient to estimate the total crop provisioning service potential of all forest ecosystems of Sri Lanka. Theoretically, the crop production data of all the crops cultivated in Sri Lanka in a given year is required to estimate monetary value of ecosystem dependent crop production . The limitation in SEEA EA is that it generates crop production data for only seven crops cultivated in Sri Lanka. It is reported that the data generated are only for “*TIER 1 preliminary reference set*” due to data limitations (SEEA 2021). There are two ways to address this problem as advised by SEEA EA; (i) upload national crop production data of all crops of Sri Lanka to “ARIES for SEEA Explorer” and proceed with machine learning or (ii) perform hand computations using national crop production secondary data using statistical software in future research. ARIES for SEEA Explorer tool has to be performed with local data in the future. Nonetheless, the results indicate that SEEA EA modeling platform could be used for valuation of ecosystem services. The monetary value of tonnes of crop production will be presented later in this report.

Crop Pollination Ecosystem Service in physical Terms (Tonnes): 2005-2018

According to the SEEA Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA) framework and major international assessments, pollination is primarily classified as a "regulating and maintenance service" (Edens, 2025). Pollination services are the ecosystem contributions by wild pollinators to the fertilization of crops that maintains or increases the abundance and/or diversity of other

species that economic units use or enjoy. Pollination service is considered as intermediate service together with soil nutrient and water supply services. The data in Table 3 indicate the crop biomass produced due to pollination services.

Table 3. Quantified crop pollination service of ecosystems

Pollination service for crop production	Pumpkin	Mango	Cocoa	Cucumber
Production 2005 (tons)	40,934	31,281	858	9,005
Production 2018 (tons)	55,356	166,773	925	14,139
Net change	14,422	135,492	67	5,134

Source: generated by SEEA EA platfor

The data indicate that quantity of crops yield produced due to the pollination ecosystem service. Once again, the data are for reference set of crops and hence further expansion of this result to more crops is required to quantify the total effect of pollination.

Global Climate Regulation Service in Physical Supply (tons C storage):2005-2018

Emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) as a result of economic and human activity and the associated changes in the atmosphere such as increase in atmospheric temperature and related drought are issues of much global concern in economic development. Ecosystems reduces of CO₂ from the atmosphere through photosynthesis and store carbon, there by help regulate climate. Table 4 shows the tones of carbon stored by ecosystems of Sri Lanka. Storage of more carbon is beneficial for a country. The data indicate that the tonnes of carbon storage has decreased in three ecosystems, namely, cropland (-1,171,274), tropical subtropical dry forest thicket (-60,261), tropical subtropical lowland rainforest (-591,698) and temperate woodland (-760). The total reduction in carbon storage sum to -1,823,996 tonnes carbon. The tonnes of carbon storage increased in all other 10 ecosystems reported is 1,830,751. Overall, the carbon storage in 2018 has increased by 6758 tons compared to 2005. The monetary value of this carbon storage is presented under monetary sub section of this report.

Soil Erosion Control Physical Supply (tons soil retained):2005-2018

Soil erosion control is a regulatory ecosystem service. The data in Table 5 shows the soil erosion data for 16 ecosystems of Sri Lanka. The data indicate that soil erosion in 2018 is lower than 2005 in boreal temperate montane forest woodland, cropland, seasonally dry tropical shrubland, tropical subtropical dry forest thicket, tropical subtropical lowland rainforest and tropical subtropical montane rainforest ecosystems. On the other hand, soil erosion in 2018 is higher than 2005 in intertidal forest shrubland, rocky pavement lava flow scree, seasonally dry tropical shrubland, temperate forest, temperate woodland, tropical subtropical savanna and urban industrial ecosystem. The erosion remained same in temperate forest, temperate sub humid grassland and warm temperate tropical marsh. The generic reasons for increased soil erosion are climate change, ex. High intensity rainfall, human activities like deforestation, tillage, flood irrigation etc. However, an important observation is that soil erosion in croplands is decreased, yet in forest lands the erosion increased. Data in Table 5 indicate largest percentage increase in soil erosion is in urban industrial ecosystem. The largest decrease in soil erosion is in seasonally dry tropical shrubland.

Table 4. Global Climate Regulation Physical Supply (tons C storage)

Year	Boreal temperate montane forest woodland	Cropland	Intertidal forest shrubland	Rocky pavement lava flow scree	Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland	Seasonally dry tropical shrubland	Temperate forest	Temperate sub humid grassland	Temperate woodland
Year 2005	545,438	29,635,777	298,968	128,440	983,872	6,467,150	948	410	141,717
Year 2018	546,679	28,464,503	316,437	134,358	1,176,251	6,535,897	948	410	140,957
Net change	1,241	-1,171,274	17,469	5,918	192,379	68,747	-	-	-760

Table 4. Continued

Year	Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket	Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest	Tropical subtropical montane rainforest	Tropical subtropical savanna	Urban industrial ecosystem	Warm temperate tropical marsh	Total
Year 2005	3,719,032	5,965,942	11,227,785	11,072,403	1,020,724	334	71,208,939
Year 2018	3,658,771	5,374,244	11,252,535	12,130,271	1,483,103	334	71,215,697
Net change	-60,261	-591,698	24,750	1,057,868	462,379	-	6,758

Table 5. Soil Erosion Control Physical Supply (tonnes soil retained)

Year	Aquatic	Boreal temperate montane forest woodland	Cropland	Intertidal forest shrubland	Rocky pavement lava flow scree	Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland	Seasonally dry tropical shrubland	Temperate forest	Temperate sub humid grassland
Year 2005	-	1,150,568	3,836,121	8,192	1,272	2,794,975	5,504,852	513	1,655
Year 2018	715	1,136,133	3,781,220	8,539	1,287	3,386,239	4,624,340	513	1,655
Net change	715	-14436	-54901	347	15	591,264	-880511	-	-

Table 5. Continued

Year	Temperate woodland	Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket	Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest	Tropical subtropical montane rainforest	Tropical subtropical savanna	Urban industrial ecosystem	Warm temperate tropical marsh	Total
Year 2005	257,872	93,378	1,477,830	33,122,680	7,988,872	3,758	155	56,242,693
Year 2018	258,963	90,806	1,455,464	32,675,645	8,761,688	60,422	155	56,243,782
Net change	1,091	-2572	-22366	-447035.51	772,816	56,663	-	1,089

Monetary Value of Ecosystem-Dependent Crop Production (2005-2018)

Monitory value of crop production is shown in Table 6. The data in Table 6 indicate the monetary value of national crop production in 2005 and 2018. Two specific information are available in this data; (i) monetary value of yearly crop production and (ii) monetary value of net change. The sum of monetary value of ecosystem-dependent crop production (for 5 crops) for the year 2018 is 213,814,588 (2015 USD). This monetary value from SEEA is based on data of 5 crops and hence it shows a fraction of the total monetary value of all crop production. In order to generate the total monetary, it is necessary to consider the crop production of all the crops reported in a given year. Examination of FAOSTAT database on monetary value of crop production of Sri Lanka in year 2018 revealed a value of 6,595,442 (constant 2014-2016 1000 USD) for 58 crops (FAOSTAT, 2025). This is a portion of the monetary value of ecosystems' crop provisioning service.

Table 6. Monetary value of ecosystem-dependent crop production

Production	SoyBean	Maize	Rice	SugarCane	Potato
Production 2005 (2015 USD)	632269	2310036	168635481	5500871	11226639
Production 2018 (2015 USD)	206675	10112507	191195419	5024913	7275074
Net change	-425594	7802471	22559938	-475958	-3951565

The data in Table 6 also shows that net change monetary value is negative for soybean, sugarcane and potato. However, the physical production data in Table 2 indicate that except sunflower and soybean crops, all the other crop produced higher yields in 2018 than 2005. Thus, the reasons for negative monetary value could be; (i) product price in 2018 is lower than 2005 (ii) depreciation of Sri Lankan currency (LKR) in 2018 compared to 2005. The product prices for 2005 and 2018 are shown in Table 7 (FAOSTAT, 2025).

Table 7. Annual weighted producer prices (USD/tonne) for some crops in 2018, Sri Lanka

Year	producer price (USD/tonne)				
	Maize	Potatoes	Rice	Soybean	Sugarcane
2005	204.8	529.7	159.4	394.7	11.8
2018	275.3	608.5	296.1	510.9	33.0

Source: FAOSTAT

All the producer prices in 2018 are higher than the 2005. Therefore, negative net monetary value is not due to lower product price in 2018. The exchange rate of LKR to USD was 101.5 LKR/USD in 2005 (Central Bank, 2025) and 162.5 LKR/USD in 2018 (Exchange rates, 2025). Therefore, the negative net monetary value could be due to increased exchange rate of Sri Lankan rupee. The most important finding in this sub section is monetary value of ecosystem dependent crop production of Sri Lanka in 2018 is 6,595,442 (constant 2014-2016 1000 USD). It was noticed that same table generated by SEEA produce slightly different numbers in different cycles. Also, an error message like “disturbed surface...” popped up during calculations.

Crop Pollination Monetary Value (2005-2018)

The ARIES SEEA EA system does not produce crop pollination monetary data shown in Table 8.

Table 8. monetary value of pollinated crops

Production	Pumpkin	Cocoa	Cucumber	Mango
Production 2005 (2015 USD)	12,632,334		2,297,673	11,015,602
Production 2018 (2015 USD)	12,983,847	1,899,725	2,739,438	44,375,907
Net change	351,514	1,899,725	441,765	33,360,305

The total monetary value of pollination – ecosystem regulatory function is 61,998,917 (2015 USD).

Global Climate Regulation Monetary Value of Change in Carbon

The data in Table 9 indicate the monetary value of carbon sequestered by the ecosystems in 2005 and 2018 have not changed and equal to 3120 Mn tons of carbon each. However, the data indicates that quantity of carbon sequestered has changed among ecosystems from 2005 and 2018, yet leaving net change unchanged. The most important message monetary value of carbon sequestered by ecosystems is 3,863,962 (2015 USD) and their contribution to regulate the effect of climate change.

Table 9. Global Climate Regulation Monetary Value of Change in Carbon

Indicator	Intertidal forest shrubland	Cropland	Urban industrial ecosystem	Temperate woodland	Tropical subtropical savanna
Quantity 2005 (tons C storage)	9,500,055	1,567,837,860	36,886,120	6,059,548	418,439,271
Quantity 2018 (tons C storage)	10,116,793	1,520,313,355	59,830,879	5,894,413	459,791,213
Net change	616,738	(47,524,505)	22,944,759	(165,135)	41,351,942
Annualised Social Cost of Carbon in 2018 (\$@2015/ton)	16	16	16	16	16
Monetary value of C sequestered (2015 USD)	9,917,149	(764,194,035)	368,951,724	(2,655,370)	664,939,222

Table 9. Continued

Indicator	Seasonally dry tropical shrubland	Rocky pavement lavaflow scree	Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland	Boreal temperate montane forest woodland	Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest
Quantity 2005 (tons C storage)	252,064,756	6,310,831	34,847,530	18,647,221	216,691,879
Quantity 2018 (tons C storage)	252,416,337	6,919,081	42,755,191	18,535,003	196,970,519
Net change	351,580	608,250	7,907,661	(112,218)	(19,721,359)
Annualised Social Cost of Carbon in 2018 (\$@2015/ton)	16	16	16	16	16
Monetary value of C sequestered (2015 USD)	5,653,413	9,780,663	127,155,196	(1,804,466)	(317,119,460)

Table 9. Continued

Indicator	Tropical subtropical montane rainforest	Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket	Aquatic	Total
Quantity 2005 (tons C storage)	411,144,953	138,416,750		3,120,103,279
Quantity 2018 (tons C storage)	406,970,761	135,810,477	763,047	3,120,103,279
Net change	(4,174,192)	(2,606,273)	763,047	-
Annualized Social Cost of Carbon in 2018 (\$@2015/ton)	16	16	16	16
Monetary value of C sequestered (2015 USD)	(67,120,999)	(41,908,867)	12,269,792	-

Conclusion

The review paper by Selivanov E., Hlav.čkov. P. (2021) describe the monetary valuation of ecosystem services.

The AI driven SEEA EA modeling platform is capable of generating physical and monetary ecosystem services for Sri Lanka. It generated physical values of ecosystem dependent crop production, pollination supported crop production, carbon sequestered and soil erosion control. The AI tool also generated monetary values of the physical quantities.

The data generated by SEEA EA modeling platform could be used for natural capital valuation of Sri Lanka. Furthermore, researchers from forestry, economics, soil science, crop science, and policy can use this tool for assessing changes in stocks, time series trend analysis and planning.

The monetary values generated could be used to compare the value of natural resources with goods and services in national accounting system.

The issues of data limitation and consistency of results was noticed. Updating more Sri Lankan data to the SEEA EA platform is recommended.

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